

PREPARING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN FOR SCHOOL BASED ON STATE STANDARDS

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Annotation: The article provides ideas on the preparation of preschool children for school education and the use of foreign experiences in developing their creative abilities.

Key words: MTT, creativity, school education, preparation, readiness to study.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 29, 2016 "On measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017-2021". PQ of September 9, 2017 "On measures to fundamentally improve the preschool education system". The PF Decree of September 30, 2017 "On measures to fundamentally improve the management of the preschool education system" is one of them. Best practices of foreign countries in preparing children for school There are very few separate literatures and research works on this topic, There are only electronic resources of the sources, including those of the Internet can be found and translated from various websites. For example, in this thread For example, B. E. Parmonov covered the best experiences of foreign countries in the article "Psychological aspects of foreign experiences in raising children in preschool education." Analytical studies of advanced experiences of countries such as Great Britain, Russian Federation, Japan, Germany. I. G. Mamajonov and R. Mamatov have partially included information on the preschool education system in the study of the "German state education system".

We know that according to the Law "On Education" of the Republic of

Uzbekistan, pre-school education and upbringing of children between the ages of six and seven also provides for a one-year compulsory preparation for primary education. Now, all children in our republic between the ages of 6 and 7 who have the ability to learn are prepared for primary classes in the 1-year preschool preparation group in state and non-state preschool education organizations and are given a certificate. This process starts much earlier in developed countries. For example, in Italy, children are prepared for school from 3 to 6 years old. This process is carried out in public kindergartens and private Catholic kindergartens. In Great Britain, the Education Act came into force in 1988, which established not only educational standards, but also a basic assessment of the level of mental development of children at the time of admission to school. Compulsory education starts at age 5 in England, Scotland and Wales, and at age 4 in Northern Ireland. That is why the start of compulsory education is considered to be the longest in Europe.

Preparing children for school is a complex, multifaceted task that covers all areas of children's lives. It is customary to distinguish a number of aspects when solving it. Firstly, the continuous development of the child's personality and his cognitive processes, which are the basis of successful educational activities in the future, and secondly, the need to teach skills and abilities such as writing, reading and calculation elements in primary school.

School readiness is the level of the child's development, which is necessary to successfully master the school curriculum without harming the child's physical, mental, social and health.

Therefore, the concept of "readiness to study" includes: physiological readiness, a good level of physical development; Psychological readiness is sufficient development of cognitive processes (attention, memory, thinking, perception, imagination, intuition, speech), learning; social readiness - the ability to communicate with peers anattention

All three components of school preparation are closely interrelated, in one way or another, deficiencies in the formation of any part affect the success of education. While preparing children for school, it is necessary to develop their creative abilities. Modern society requires creative, ordinary people who direct their energy for the benefit of humanity. In this regard, the main task of modern education is to educate a creative, independent and free person, because the person who determines the development of the future is creativity. According to the President's decision, the concept of development of the preschool education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 was approved and it envisages the implementation of the following tasks: further improvement of the normative legal framework in the field of preschool education, all-round intellectual, moral, creating conditions for aesthetic and physical development; increase coverage of children with quality pre-school education, ensure equal access to it, develop public-private partnership in this field; introducing innovations, advanced pedagogical and information-communication technologies into the preschool education system; improving the management system of preschool education, ensuring the transparency and efficiency of financing the activities of preschool educational institutions, introducing a completely new approach to the training, retraining, upgrading, selection and development of preschool education system employees in the preschool education system . The value of creative development is determined by the fact that it contributes to children's new knowledge, changes that enrich their world, and the manifestation of personal qualities of a preschooler. In creative activity, learning the surrounding reality, the child is constantly discovering new things, such as "new activity".

The initial conditions for the creative expression of an adult begin with the period of preschool education. Therefore, it is necessary to study the process and the formation of creative development in the early stages of personality development in preschool children. The basis for personal development in

psychological and pedagogical sciences is the presence of a constant thought about this process. The creative development of a preschool child takes place in front of him. Different types of activities: game, visual, constructive, musical, theater, work are important in the formation of personality.

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